

Appendix 2. Summary of Gamification Strategies Identified

Study	Objective (What did they aim to achieve?)	Methodology (What did they do?)	Results (What did they achieve?)
P1	Increase productivity, loyalty, and efficiency, and reduce turnover in a hybrid environment.	Implementation of a gamified organizational environment based on a points system and individual rewards.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 50% increase in sprint velocity. • Slight improvement in loyalty and job satisfaction.
P2	Increase productivity of individuals affected by procrastination.	ProScore framework using a points system to encourage competition.	Functional framework to combat procrastination through competition.
P3	Influence team productivity considering Social and Human Factors (SHF).	Custom method based on gamification and SHF.	Method defined to design strategies and measure indicators according to context.
P4	Improve productivity in agile retrospectives focusing on SHF.	Ga-Starfish gamification strategy based on the starfish technique addressing five moments: “Start doing,” “Stop doing,” “Do more,” “Do less,” and “Keep doing,” incorporating SHF.	Strategy designed and validated through expert judgment and pilot testing.
P5	Evaluate the impact of gamification on software productivity in higher education.	Gamification strategy designed in five phases (Context, Gamification Environment Design, Evaluation Environment Design, Technological Support, and Execution) based on a method incorporating SHF.	Design and implementation of a gamification strategy for a Software Engineering course in a higher education institution using Moodle over an 18-week academic period.
P6	Increase the adoption of agile methodologies, specifically Scrum, in a poultry startup in Indonesia.	Application of the 6D gamification framework and implementation of the “Trophies for Jira Dashboard” tool in Scrum environments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gamification had a 69.4% impact on the success of Agile adoption. • Significant improvement in motivation, personal growth, collaboration among colleagues, and early problem resolution
P7	Encourage continuous collaboration among software development team members in knowledge transfer.	GamifiK strategy supported by gamification elements and SHF, based on a model and a clearly structured five-phase method.	The strategy generated a significant improvement in productivity, as the estimation of developed and accepted story points per sprint increased.

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P8	Mitigate resistance to change in Software Process Improvement (SPI) initiatives and improve team productivity.	Gamification strategy called Interplanetary Mission, composed of five phases (Context, Gamification Environment Design, Evaluation Environment Design, Support, and Execution) based on a model integrating: (1) Social and Human Factors (SHF), (2) Gamification, and (3) Productivity.	The strategy was implemented in a business context (IT area of the @Medellín project), incorporating elements such as progression, narrative, rewards, rankings, and challenges (missions), promoting SHF like motivation and serving as an alternative to reduce lack of commitment and knowledge gaps in management.
P9	Transform Scrum-based software development into a fun and motivating activity to increase the execution of tasks.	Gamification experience centered on a prototype tool called RUPGY, an extension of Redmine, integrating game design elements into task management.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement in planning and organization of daily tasks. • Increased developer engagement in task execution and better iteration scheduling.
P10	Intervene in the software improvement process in the automotive industry based on gamification and SHF.	Gamification strategy applied in the automotive software development context in an ad hoc manner, without a specific gamification design tool.	Ability of the strategy to promote SHF, including motivation, commitment, team cohesion, emotional intelligence, and autonomy.
P11	Demonstrate how specific gamification elements can enhance human factors (SHF) that increase productivity in software development.	Use of the multicriteria method SAW (Simple Additive Weighting) to prioritize which gamification elements most affect productivity.	Precise identification of gamification elements (mechanics, dynamics, and components) with the greatest influence on SHF.